

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEMS. REFRACTOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS OF POLAR CRYSTALS IN B₂O₃-GLASS.

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The mole réfraction of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl and CsCl dissolved in boric oxide glass has been measured and the deformation of the crystals calculated.

Fajans and Joos (*Z. Physik*, 1921, **97**, 304) postulated the mutual effect of neighbouring ions in polarising their electron sheaths. Certain regularities have been observed by Fajans and his co-workers in various systems, viz., solid crystalline state, aqueous solution and in the gaseous state. An excellent summary of the experimental results in aqueous solution has been given by Fajans and others (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1928, **34**, 2). Although much work has been done on the above lines comparatively little work has been done in studying the deforming effect of typical polar crystals when dissolved in a homogeneous glass, preferably not exerting any chemical action. Wulff and Majumdar (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, **31B**, 319) studied the system $x\text{Na}_2\text{O}$, $y\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$. The subject has also been studied by Tilton and Tool (*Bureau of Standards J.*, 1929, **3**, 619), Faik and Finn (*ibid.*, 1931, **6**, 993), Hubbard and Finn (*ibid.*, 1935, **14**, 133) and Morew and Merwin (*J. Opt. Soc. Amer.*, 1932, **22**, 632).

Recently Biltz and his co-workers have carried out a systematic investigation on the subject of additivity of constituents in the glass system (Biltz, Weibke and Schraeder-Träger, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1937, **234**, 253) and have concluded that strict additivity still persists when constituents enter into the composition of a glass system : " Die Molrefraktion einfacher Gläser ist eine eindeutig und streng additive Grösse." (*Glastech. Ber.*, 1938, **16**, 131). Kordes (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1939, **241**, 1, 418), on the other hand, disputes the above conclusion of Biltz. It was therefore decided to prepare solid solutions of polar crystals like LiCl, NaCl, KCl, RbCl and CsCl in boric oxide glass and measure the refractive index and density of the samples and hence calculate the deformation produced in the crystals.

Various methods have been suggested for determining the deformation of ions and molecules, based on measurement of dielectric constant, refractive index, etc. It is well known that in the Clausius-Mosotti equation, if

the dielectric constant is replaced by square of the refractive index (for infinitely long waves), then we get the Lorenz and Lorentz equation

$$r = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{1}{d},$$

where r is the specific refraction. By multiplying both sides of this equation by M , the molecular weight, we get R , the mole refraction, given by the equation

$$R = \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d}$$

R , which is expressed in c.c., is a measure of the molar polarisation (electron polarisation if measurements are made with the visible range of the spectrum).

It is well known that paths of electrons undergo change when brought in an external electric field, the magnitude of the deviation depending upon strength of the applied field (Stark effect). It is natural to expect, therefore, that when the electron sheath of an ion and also to a limited extent of neutral molecules comes in the vicinity of another ion, a deformation should occur, which may be likened to the Stark effect in a homogeneous field. The deformation, which really represents a sum total effect of various factors, is at best only a qualitative indication of mutual interaction of charged particle in the system. In some cases, the phenomenon has been quantitatively explained in the light of the more recent theory of resonance, as for example in the case of the HCl molecule, but up till now, no general quantitative explanation is available. Fajans and his co-workers have deduced certain regularities guiding deformation in general. The cation is usually the deforming and the anion the deformed ion. Actually there are several effects to be taken in account, namely the mutual interactions of the respective nuclei and the peripheral charges. These effects are, however, not all equally strong and we are left with the one effect which preponderates over the rest, namely, the deforming effect of the negative sheath of the anion by the positive sheath of the cation. It follows, therefore, that with the same anion, a smaller radius of the cation of the same valency will mean a stronger deformation of the anion and this will of course increase with higher valency of the cation. The general conclusions of Fajans and Joos may be briefly summarised as follows: (i) The deformability of ions increases with increasing atomic number. (ii) An anion is more deformable than the cation; the greater the charge of the ion, the greater the deformation. (iii) The deforming power of the cation increases with the charge and diminishes with the ionic diameter.

If r represents the specific refraction of a mixture of, say, two components, whose mole refractions in the pure state are r_1 and r_2 and p , the percentage of the first component in the mixture, then, if there is no mutual interaction of the components in the mixture, the additivity law will hold good, *i.e.*,

$$100r = pr_1 + (100-p)r_2.$$

Any deviation from the additivity formula will point to deformation in the system. If the solvent be assumed to be unaffected, which probably is not strictly true, the deviation from the additivity formula will afford us a means of at least qualitatively defining deformation of the solute.

In a system consisting of $p\%$ of XCl and $(100-p)\%$ of B_2O_3 , if we determine the refractive index n_D for sodium light and the density d of the system, then we can calculate the value of r_2 from the above equation after finding out the value of r for the mixture from the Lorenz-Lorentz equation, taking a constant value of r_1 , which is taken to be 0.151 c.c. (Wulff and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*). By multiplying this value of r_2 by the molecular weight of XCl, we get the mole refraction of XCl in the glass. This value may be usefully compared with those of XCl in the crystal on the one hand and in state of infinite dilution in aqueous solution on the other.

For absolute value of R , an extrapolated value of refractive index, n_∞ , should be used in the Lorenz-Lorentz equation. But for comparative purpose in which absolute values are not involved, the value of refractive index n_D for sodium light may be conveniently used.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Samples—Boric oxide (Merck *pro Analyse* quality) was twice recrystallised from hot water and dried in a vacuum desiccator for 7 days until absolutely anhydrous as tested by anhydrous copper sulphate with its solution in absolute alcohol. Unless special precautions are taken in dehydration, the molten B_2O_3 glass will tenaciously retain traces of moisture, which would later interfere with the value of a mole refraction, R . A better method, which could not unfortunately be followed, would be to use an induction oven of high frequency in high vacuum (10^{-4} to 10^{-6} mm), using an ordinary oil pump and a couple of secondary mercury diffusion pumps, as used by Wulff and Majumdar (*loc. cit.*). The error involved, however, is not regarded sufficiently high to affect comparative results which the present communication claims.

The chlorides of lithium, sodium, potassium, rubidium and caesium were Merck's reagent quality products and were carefully dehydrated for a pretty long time. Lithium chloride, which is very hygroscopic, was evaporated to dryness in a platinum dish and maintained at a temperature of 400-500° in an electric oven for several hours.

Samples of boric oxide and alkali chloride in varying proportions were taken in platinum crucible and heated in an electric furnace at a temperature of 900-1000° for several hours in order to ensure thorough homogeneous mixing of the ingredients. A portion was sublimed at first but after a time a melt of constant composition was obtained. The crucible was then removed from the furnace and quickly chilled by placing it on a cool surface, when the solidified glass cracked. The solid was then taken out with the help of a sharp-pointed knife, transferred to a sample tube and kept within a vacuum desiccator. Before each experiment the sample was first dipped in absolute alcohol, then in pure toluene and finally quickly dried in a blast of hot air. In this way any superficial layer of hydroxide formed was washed out and the glass presented a thoroughly transparent appearance.

The above method of preparation of samples is not free from objection. Molten boric oxide has a different coefficient of cubical expansion from platinum and in consequence of this when the melt solidifies great stress is brought to bear upon the system. This might render the glass double diffracting, a fact which can be easily verified by suspending the solid in a liquid and examining it in a polarisation microscope with crossed nicols. Each sample was examined in this way before further optical examination and only those pieces, which remained dark in all positions with crossed nicols, were selected.

Analysis of the Samples.—A weighed amount of the anhydrous sample was taken in a weighed platinum crucible, treated repeatedly with a mixture of hydrofluoric and sulphuric acids (both of Merck's reagent quality) and was first evaporated on asbestos to drive off boron trifluoride and then strongly ignited over Mecker burner; the residue was cooled in a desiccator and weighed as alkali sulphate. In this way, the amount of alkali chloride was calculated and by subtracting this weight from the original weight of the glass, the proportion of boric oxide was determined.

Density Determination.—It is well known that density of solids cannot be determined with the same degree of accuracy as in the case of liquids. Different investigators have tried to determine the density of solids by the pycnometer method using liquids of high density as thallium ethylate; solu-

tion of double iodide of mercury and potassium, methylene iodide, acetylene tetrabromide, various borotungstate solutions, etc.

Day and Allen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 37) using a pycnometer of about 25 c.c. capacity containing 5-10 g. of solid substance obtained satisfactory results, the error not exceeding one unit in the fourth decimal place. But the method has not proved satisfactory in the case of smaller particles and was therefore modified by Johnston and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 566). The pycnometer method thus requires special modification for determining crystal densities. Lord Berkeley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 56) obtained satisfactory results by using carbon tetrachloride as the immersion liquid. Baxter and Wallace (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 259) used toluene as the floatation medium but the method did not give reproducible results, the error being in the region of 5%.

The technique of the floatation method was first developed by Retger (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1889, 3, 289) and later by Wulff and Heigl (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 153A, 187). The floatation method is in general superior to the immersion method for determination of crystal densities. The method is worked on the principle that a solid will only just float at all points of a liquid only if it has the same density as the liquid itself. The range of densities covered by this method depends on the densities of liquids available as standard liquids. Acetylene tetrabromide and methylene iodide are particularly suitable for use as the heavy liquids and benzene or toluene, carefully dehydrated, may be used as the light standard liquid. Methylene iodide has an approximate density of 3.5 and by diluting it with benzene the density of the mixture may be reduced to 0.9. Acetylene tetrabromide, which has a density of about 2.96, can also be conveniently used for density determinations. The method is quite accurate if the temperature of the liquid mixture is carefully controlled. The chief error of the method lies in the adherence of a thin layer of air to the surface of the sample. As a result of this, when a powder consisting of small particles is used, at a certain point some particles will be found to rise and others to fall at the same time. But in spite of this error, density determined by the floatation method is correct up to 5 in the fourth place of decimals. A simplified method analogous to that used by Wulff and Heigl (*loc. cit.*) has been used in this investigation.

In the present investigation, acetylene tetrabromide (Merck), redistilled under reduced pressure and redistilled toluene, previously dried over metallic sodium, have been used as the heavier and lighter liquid respectively. A large weighing bottle A (100 c.c.) fitted with a specially made ground glass stopper was suspended in a transparent thermostat maintained at $35^{\circ} \pm .05$.

The stopper has three openings. *a*, for introducing the lighter liquid, *b*, for introducing a current of air under pressure and *c*, for forcing the liquid into the pyknometer. The end of the tube *c* is fitted by ground glass joint into one of the side-tubes of a specially made pyknometer (capacity about 24 c.c.). The pyknometer had two glass stop-cocks, which were made air-tight by using the minimum amount of a paste of dextrin in glycerine, which had been found to be best suited for the purpose. The actual procedure including removal of excess of liquid sticking to the inside of open tubes above the stop-cocks is very important for the purpose of getting reproducible results. After cleaning the pyknometer in the usual way, it was dried by suction and the minimum quantity of white vaseline was used in the stop-cocks; any excess of it, outside the stop-cocks and within the protruding tube was carefully wiped off repeatedly with clean linen and rolled filter paper. It was then weighed empty using a dummy counterpoise of approximately the same shape and size to correct for buoyancy and moisture. Both the pyknometer and the dummy were left in the balance for a sufficiently long time to ensure full deposition of moisture under the conditions. The pyknometer was then filled with distilled water, placed in the thermostat and a similar procedure was followed before weighing. As the liquids used in the method dissolved vaseline, the dextrine paste in glycerine was used instead and the weight of the empty pyknometer determined again in a similar manner.

FIG. 1.
Suspension vessel and pyknometer.

About 50 c.c. of acetylene tetrabromide were taken in vessel A (Fig. 1), placed in the thermostat and a piece of tested glass previously treated was dropped into it. The latter usually floated up on account of its lower density. Purified toluene was now gradually introduced through the opening *a*, drop by drop and the solution stirred by bubbling dry air through *b*. In this way a point was reached at which the particle remained suspended within the mixture in any position. The method is quite sensitive and one or two drops

of either liquid reverses the course of the particle, the exact point being determined by adding forwards and backwards several times until the desired point was reached. The ground end of the pyknometer tube was next joined to the end of the side-tube, *c*, of the suspension vessel. Both the stop-cocks of the pyknometer were then opened, the side-tube, *a*, closed and air was blown through *b*, until the pyknometer was filled. The connection with the side-tube was next broken and the pyknometer allowed to remain in the thermostat for some more time. The usual precautions were taken before weighing the pyknometer. Two independent measurements were made with each sample and the mean value of density taken.

Determination of the Refractive Index.—The refractive index determination of crystals and small pieces of glass is a matter of considerable difficulty. The Pulfrich refractometer, which is excellently suited for liquids, can be used with transparent solids, if the latter is carefully ground so as to give it the shape of a right-angled prism. It was then placed directly on top of the prism of the instrument and the measurement is carried out in the same way as in the case of a liquid. As boric oxide is hygroscopic even in the solidified state of glass, although much less than in the non-fused solid state, this method could not be employed. It is also difficult to realise experimentally optically plane ground surfaces. Another method, the best so far proposed, is due to Wulff and Heigl (*loc. cit.*). According to this method a fine pencil of homogeneous light is made to undergo interference through a fine slit. One part of the interfered ray passes through the solid suspended in a liquid and the other part through the suspension medium, which is contained in a glass trough provided with plane parallel sides. In consequence of difference in refractivity of the solid and the liquid, the interference bands which are observed through a telescope on the other side are bent. Two liquids are chosen, one having a slightly higher and the other a slightly lower refractive index than the solid and the composition of the suspending medium gradually changed until the interference bands become again straight. At this point the liquid mixture and the solid have the same refractivity. With a specially constructed refractometer, the refractive index of the former is measured from above. In the present investigation the refractive index of the glasses have been measured by the Becke method. A source of error which could not unfortunately be eliminated lay in the fact that the density determinations were carried out at 35°, whereas the refractive indices were determined at the room temperature. Properly speaking a correction factor has to be applied for difference of temperature. As is well known, however, the temperature coefficient of refractive index is smaller than the experimental error of the method and for comparative results the error will not be

appreciable. The Becke method is based on the principle of total reflection of light passing from a denser to a rarer medium when the incidence is outside the critical angle. The method was first used for crystals by Schröder von der Kolk ("Kurze Anleitung zur mikroskopischen Kristallbestimmung", Wiesbaden, 1898). It consists in making the refractive index of a liquid mixture agree as far as possible with that of a fragment of a crystal immersed in it by altering its composition and then determining the refractive index of the mixture by the usual method. Small fragments of the glass were placed in a trough mounted on a slide and covered with one of two selected liquids. It follows from optical considerations that if on raising the eye-piece of the microscope after focussing the object, the bright lines of contact tend to go out of the solid, then the liquid has a higher refractivity than the solid. On the other hand, if on raising the eye-piece, the lines of contact appear to converge within the solid, the reverse is the case. Drops of the second liquid were then added to the first and the object viewed in a dark room illuminated by sodium light. In this way two liquid mixtures were obtained for the same sample of glass, one possessing a slightly higher and the other a slightly lower refractive index than the sample. These mixtures were then examined in an ordinary Pulfrich refractometer in sodium light and the mean of the two values taken. Usually the variation

TABLE I.

System: LiCl—B ₂ O ₃ .			System: RbCl—B ₂ O ₃ .		
LiCl.	Density.	n _D .	RbCl.	Density.	n _D .
14.35%	1.9586	1.4515	28.96%	2.1445	1.4657
20.43	2.0052	1.4495	38.20	2.2226	1.4523
25.79	2.0392	1.4480	45.74	2.2664	1.4374
System: CsCl—B ₂ O ₃ .			System: NaCl—B ₂ O ₃ .		
CsCl.	Density.	n _D .	NaCl.	Density.	n _D .
44.07%	2.4683	1.5234	30.63%	2.0321	1.4681
52.72	2.6534	1.5401	35.64	2.0385	1.4630
57.48	2.7725	1.5525	38.07	2.0422	1.4585
System: KCl—B ₂ O ₃ .			System: NaCl—B ₂ O ₃ .		
KCl.	Density.	n _D .	NaCl.	Density.	n _D .
25.32%	2.0441	1.4843	47.92	2.0556	1.4470
48.86	2.0824	1.4665	52.12	2.3425	1.4313
56.31	2.0536	1.4584			
68.64	2.1045	1.4542			

was in the fourth place of decimals, which for solids may be regarded as satisfactory. The following liquids were used for the purpose: toluene, carbon tetrachloride and purified kerosene oil. Before proceeding with any piece it was tested in the polarisation microscope to see whether it was doubly diffracting or not and only those pieces were taken which were optically isotropic.

In the following tables the values of r_{KCl} and hence R_{KCl} for the alkali chloride are calculated from the mixture law; the respective values of R at infinite dilution in aqueous solution and in crystal are shown in the last column. The value of r for B_2O_3 is taken as 0.151 (Wulff and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

System: $\text{LiCl}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$.					
LiCl.	$r_{\text{mix. (exp.)}$	$r_{\text{LiCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{LiCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{sol.}}$	$R_{\text{cryst.}}$
14.35%	0.1375	0.0571	2.42	8.76	7.59
20.43	0.1339	0.0675	2.86	Fajans, Kohner and Geffcken (<i>Z. Elektrochem.</i> , 1925, 34, 2).	
25.79	0.1313	0.0748	3.17		

TABLE III.

System: $\text{NaCl}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$.					
NaCl.	$r_{\text{mix. (exp.)}$	$r_{\text{NaCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{NaCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{sol.}}$	$R_{\text{cryst.}}$
30.63%	0.1369	0.1051	6.14	9.27	8.52
35.64	0.1351	0.1064	6.21	Fajans, Kohner and Geffcken (<i>loc. cit.</i>).	
38.07	0.1337	0.1060	6.22		
47.92	0.1300	0.1072	6.26		

TABLE IV.

System: $\text{KCl}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$.					
KCl.	$r_{\text{mix. (exp.)}$	$r_{\text{KCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{KCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{sol.}}$	$R_{\text{cryst.}}$
25.32%	0.1399	0.1074	8.41	11.31	10.833
48.86	0.1349	0.1140	8.52	Wulff and Schaller (<i>loc. cit.</i>).	
56.31	0.1309	0.1154	8.61		
68.61	0.1275	0.1168	8.72		

TABLE V.

System: $\text{RbCl}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$.					
RbCl.	$r_{\text{mix. (exp.)}$	$r_{\text{RbCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{RbCl (calc.)}$	$R_{\text{sol.}}$	$R_{\text{cryst.}}$
28.96%	0.1288	0.0743	8.98	12.84	12.55
38.20	0.1215	0.0740	8.96	Wulff and Schaller (<i>loc. cit.</i>).	
45.74	0.1157	0.0739	8.94		
47.13	0.1146	0.0738	8.93		
52.12	0.1106	0.0736	8.90		

TABLE VI.

System : CsCl—B₂O₃.

CsCl.	r_{mix} (exp.).	r_{CsCl} (calc.).	R_{CsCl} (calc.).	R_{sol} .	R_{cryst} .
44.07%	0.1239	0.0897	15.10	15.60	15.30
52.72	0.1183	0.0891	15.00	Wulff and Heigl (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	
57.48	0.1153	0.0890	14.91		

DISCUSSION.

It is interesting to discuss how far the mole refraction of alkali chlorides in solid solution in a medium of high viscosity like B₂O₃, calculated from the additivity formula, on the assumption that the mole refraction of the solvent remains constant, tally with those found for infinite dilution in aqueous solution on the one hand and the value in crystals of the pure salts on the other. The value of R in the crystal is in every case, as may be easily expected, less than that in aqueous solution at infinite dilution for obvious effects of deformation in the closely packed solid state. It would also be interesting to discuss the variation of R_{XCl} in solid solution with concentration and to compare it with the corresponding aqueous solution. It should be observed, however, that the errors involved in refractive index determination in our case are relatively large compared with the methods followed by the workers of the Fajans school and therefore no great claim is made about the absolute values of R . They can, however, be safely utilised for comparative purposes and are not to be confused with standard values.

It is to be expected from the Fajans theory that smaller the cation, for the same valency the greater will be its deforming action on a particular anion with consequent lowering in the value of R for the salt. LiCl should therefore show the largest amount of divergence between R_{sol} and R_{cryst} , the respective values being 8.76 and 7.59 c.c. What strikes us, however, is its extremely low value in solid solution, varying between 2.52 and 3.17 c.c. for the concentration range investigated. Such wide departure from the value in the crystal state and in solution in water may only be attributed to particularly strong deformation. This will not be explained by change of dielectric constant alone, although it undoubtedly plays an important role, as in the same medium CsCl shows but little divergence—a fact which can be easily explained on the basis of the Fajans theory. Hence the dielectric constant factor is not alone sufficient to explain the abnormal lowering in the value of mole refraction in the case of LiCl. It is, however, surprising

that the value can be lowered from 7.52 c.c. in the case of the crystal to 2.42 c.c. in solid solution. The concentration effect of LiCl in aqueous solution has not been unfortunately thoroughly studied in the past although the change of R for LiClO₄ for different concentrations is available (Geffcken, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 88, 113). The value of R in this case increases with concentration, which is also found to be the case with LiCl in the present case.

In the case of NaCl, the divergence of R from R_{cryst} is marked although not so great as in the case of LiCl. The maximum value 6.26 c.c. in our case may be compared with 8.5 c.c. for the pure crystal.

The value of R , however, increases instead of decreasing with concentration as in the case of the aqueous solution, although the increase is less marked than in the case of the previous salt. The same phenomenon is noticed in the case of KCl, in which case also R shows slight increase with concentration. But in both the cases the respective values of R are decidedly smaller than R_{cryst} .

In the case of RbCl, the variation of R with concentration is much smaller and the order follows that for aqueous solution, although the individual values still show some amount of divergence.

The most interesting case is that of CsCl. Here although concentration has slight lowering effect as in the case of the aqueous solution but the values do not markedly differ from that of R_{cryst} . The minimum value in our case is found to be 14.99 as against 15.20 c.c. for crystal. This is a striking confirmation of the Fajans' rule even in solid solution.

The dielectric constant of B₂O₃ glass according to Thomas (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 85, 2109) has a value 3.5. The different alkali borates have values lying between 6.44 and 7.50 (Landolt Börnstein Tabellen, 1923, II, 1033), compared with water these values are remarkably small. It may be expected therefore that lower dielectric constant of the medium will cause a closer approach of the constituent ions of the crystal in solid solution causing a strong deformation. This would be a purely electrostatic effect. This effect will be more or less identical with different polar crystals of the type XCl in the same medium if dielectric constant alone were the deciding factor. The fact that LiCl is most strongly and CsCl very feebly deformed in the same medium lends strong support to the view that the small cation having a large surface density of charge strongly polarises the anion, while the comparatively large cation with a smaller surface density of charge brings about but little polarisation of the anion. Wulff and Majumdar (*loc. cit.*) investigating the system $x\text{Na}_2\text{O}$, $y\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ arrived at a similar conclusion that Na₂B₄O₇ in solid solution in B₂O₃ is very strongly deformed and the deform-

ation produced is of a much higher order than in the crystal or in aqueous solution.

This means that LiCl exists in all probability in the associated (as opposed to ionised) state in solid solution of glass. The co-valent nature of the binding force progressively changes into electrovalent until CsCl is reached, in which even in the glass state, the constituents are most likely in the same condition as in the crystal.

The reason why the slope of the concentration-mole refraction curves show an opposite sign to those in the case of corresponding aqueous solutions may be explained as due to the mutual effect of the constituent ions of the electrolyte on the solvent medium.

Hence it can be asserted that the view point of Biltz that in every case the mole refraction of the constituents persists as additive functions when they go to form a glass system is untenable. This is only true in case of polar crystals having a comparatively large cation. Moreover, the polarising power of the cation for a particular anion follows the inequality :

and this is fully consistent with the postulates of Fajans theory of deformation.

The lattice distances of the alkali halides in the same solvent have been measured by the Debye-Scherer method and certain interesting departures have been observed. This will form the subject matter of a future communication.

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